

Pakistan's Role in War against Terrorism and Challenges Faced by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's Police in the Contemporary Phase

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November ,2025</p> <p>Accepted: February ,2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Police, National Counter Terrorism Authority, Federally Administered Tribal Areas, Frontier Crimes Regulation, Dispute Resolution Councils, Police Assistant Line.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18485902</p>	<p><i>In the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan, the threat of terrorism has been efficiently handled and faced by the regions police department. The terrorism threat needed to be managed in a realistic manner. The federal and provincial governments had supported the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police. Modern weapons and equipment was also present at the disposal of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police force to combat terrorists efficiently. The terrorism were stopped from performing their activities only because of timely actions such as blocking their networks and destroying their sanctuaries were taken by the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Force with Army of Pakistan backing them. This whole operation required a lot of sacrifices to be made by them. The whole war on terror was a lost cause if necessary sacrifices were not made by the police forces and the armed forces at the right time. The public and police were mentally and physically affected due to aftershocks of the terrorist activities that left a mark on their minds and bodies. Both good and bad influence was witnessed by it. The police role should always be appreciated because of their proper planning in restraining the threat of terrorism. In terms of domestic security challenges, the police also disassociated militants nearby relations and the instant result witnessed in crime reduction. The topic needs serious investigation as the role in counter-terrorism strategies was normally dominated by military and police is just considered as helping hands. Moreover, it is very important to investigate the Pakistan's Role in War against Terrorism and Challenges Faced by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's Police.</i></p>

Introduction

Two main events caused the 2008 elections to be conducted: the revolution of Black Coat (lawyers), which pursued the restoration of the sovereign courts terminated by General Musharraf in March 2007 and Benazir Bhutto's assassination in December 2007. Pakistan People's Party had the emotional soft corner in the nation's heart which led them to have sympathy vote. Pakistan People's Party won the election of 2008 and were expected to deliver on their promises by maintain law and order situation in the country. However, from the past four years, all the negative aspects of a governing body had been exposed in the tenure of the Pakistan People's Party as bad governance, exploitation of authorities and corruption was at its peak. The law and order situation in the country being forsake and taken lightly was the major casualty under the Pakistan People's Party government. In 2017, the well-defined Police Act 2017 was introduced in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This act focused on the establishment of a counter-terrorism unit, rapid action force, forensic labs and active mobile unit to meet the contemporary challenges.

Literature Review

We came know that State of Pakistan is already familiar with terrorism when we study the terrorism concept and its idea. The Soviet Union "Infidel Communists" were planned to be countered by the help of the religious Jihad Forces (Malik, 2008). Mujahidin were properly trained at Islamic schools/madrassas and at training camps. The United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia aided these Islamic madrassas and training camps, with them physically being located in Pakistan and Afghanistan but moving forward with a framework provided by the United States (US) (Malik, 2005). Different Terrorist organizations established themselves in Pakistan through these camps and madrassas. Various criminal gangs shook hand with these terrorist (Hussain, 2012). They had their own demands according to their needs from the government of Pakistan and denied the supremacy of the State (Rana, 2014). The settling of Afghan refugees also welcomed a bunch of issues with it such as increase in human trafficking, drug dealing and weapon smuggling was witnessed which in response boosted the dealing of narcotics, building up the Kalashnikov lifestyle, and small arms and light weapons growth (Dolan, 2011).

Conceptual Framework

Farzana Sheikh in “Making sense of Pakistan” one of her book inspected and highlights that ever since gaining independence in 1947, Pakistan has always been a victim to poor social, economic and political strategies. This has been one of the root causes of terrorism in Pakistan and the military has benefited from these kinds of situations. Rather than being the guardian of Islam as directed by the father of nation, a negative image of Pakistan has been emerged, based on who is governing the country (Vitali, 2014). This research aims to study the role of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police in counter-terrorism strategies. Thus, the research will be an addition in understanding the challenges faced by police in counter-terrorism strategies.

Discussion

What are the challenges to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police and what reforms are needed in the contemporary phase to make police an ideal police of Pakistan?

Currently, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has seventy thousand men and women employed in the police department with a responsibility of maintaining peace and stability over the population of 26 million.

Police administrative structure

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is divided into six regions and each region is commanded by Regional Police Officers (RPO) Police headquarters, known as Central Police Office (CPO) is situated in Peshawar. The contemporary police department is working under Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Act 2017 that is considered a milestone in sophisticating the police department to meet contemporary security needs and challenges. For special operations and counter-terrorism, a group of six thousand trained ‘Elite force’ has been formed under Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 2017 Police Act. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Bureau of Investigation assisted by four Deputy Inspector General of Police (DIGs) is responsible for criminal investigation management (Khan, 2014).

Police responsibilities and mode of operations

According to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa police act 2017, police owns following attitude and responsibilities toward local community.

1. Police should maintain a pattern of decorum and courtesy in the province
2. Police should endorse peace in society.
3. Police members should protect people who are being exposed to physical damage especially minorities, female and infants.
4. Police should safeguard life, property, and honor of locals;
5. Sniff out all the criminals and deliver them punishments according to their crimes.
6. Police should counter anti-state activities or personnel in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa
7. To design or operate secret or open operations against harmful, criminal and violent actors.

Organization of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police

The headquarter of Police is situated in Peshawar and includes a whole lot of importance segments such as Brand of Legal affairs, Brand of Inside Accountability and Brand of Public Relation. The Police Establishment split into higher and lower ranks police officers. Police Ranks of Higher levels includes (a) Provincial Police Officer (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Act, 2017)

Reforms In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Sector

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Act 2017 and provincial leadership has introduced following reforms in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa police department.

1. Directorate of Police Complaints

From traditional phase to contemporary age, police officers were considered as ruler of the appointed area and they were hardly questioned for the use of their powers. So, the political/ security powers appointed to police officers were often misused. According to estimates, the police department is considered as a most corrupt institute in Pakistan (Pakistan corruption report, 2017). Therefore, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa administration has established Directorate of police complaint under Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Act 2017, to increase internal liability, stringent disciplinary acts and local community participation in identifying corrupt police officers. During 2017, 339 corrupt police officers were suspended from their jobs and about 5000 corrupt police officers faced corruption trials in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (PIPS Report, 2011).

2. Police training institutes

One of the drawbacks in police efficiency is lack of proper training during job tenure. So Khyber Pakhtunkhwa government has established new schools for police training to improve human resource and capacity structure.

3. Department of counter-terrorism

According to Khalid (2017), Counter terrorism is an institutional terminology which requires six key components;

1. Targets or strike patterns could be investigated and pinpointed using valid intelligence information

2. Creating forces with sole purpose of removing threat, if repulsion is impossible then to halt to terminate any reported threat by any means possible.
3. Whenever a terrorist activity is witnessed, the situation should be handled and contained immediately.
4. The environment should be friendly as it would allow better communication of information and to allow reprisal operations on said intelligence once verified to further preempt any imminent threats.
5. In the whole operation, the role of police is very important in taking action against terrorist and collective any kind of important information.
6. The contemporary role of police is not suitable to police sufficient operational and technical leverage over the counterterrorism policy and where police as a department is further distributed into forces that are actually purpose built for rendering counter terrorism services, police department as a whole requires structural amendments to suit coming threats.

Cheema (2016) mentions that counter terrorism requires all the law enforcement institution to work together and cooperate with each other and have credibility and credence and any institution if taken selectively, would result in fractures in the counter terrorism framework and would lead to ambiguities that can be tactically and strategically dent counterterrorism. In Pakistan, there has been serious negligence in policy making institutes on police capacity building and engaging police in counter-terrorism, since last many years.

Meanwhile looking at weak infrastructure and capability of police, Pakistan Army has been given the task of fighting terrorism which was not their job even (Special Report, 2010). Army adopted hard approaches to curb militancy in Pakistan and started operation in two areas, one in Federally Administered Tribal Agency (FATA), area adjacent to Afghanistan ruled under Frontier Crimes Regulation (FCR) 1901, and second in Swat a city in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa that comes in Malakand division where operation has been completed but the army is still there. Article 245 was invoked by the government for operation in these two areas; therefore, with reference to this army can be called in aid of civil power whenever it is needed (Rana, 2014).

The operation started mainly due to military's strong capability, as it had been managing Afghan affairs since long and the region is bordered with Afghanistan (Zant, 2015). But as the army was not trained for non-conventional warfare, it had to bear huge losses in terms of life and infrastructure at earlier stages in FATA (Hilali, 2005). The figure tells that in 2009 army lost the lives of 350 soldiers and with the passage of time it started knowing the war pattern, so the loss of lives was reduced to 198 in 2013 (Perito, 2014)

Swat operation was named as operation Rah e Haq. The initial operation initiated by the army in opposition to Tehreek-e-Nafaz-e-Shariat-e-Mohammadi (TNSM), an organization governed Sufi Muhammad which was a great success for the army (Khan, 2012). Pakistan army initiated second operation launched which was Operation Rah-e-Nijat (REH) to recapture the region Shangla. Initially, the terrorist activities showed weakness of the police. Mullah Fazullah was the leader of the local Taliban's and police being afraid of them started to join their ranks. Mullah Fazullah is now the head of Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP). However, police were supposed to manage the area after the operation was finished, but such high risk area could not be handled by police so the army had to step in the situation and take charge.

Moreover, some serious scandals were unveiled after the operations in Swat and FATA were successfully concluded. Army was considered messiah by many and they were loved by the people, but few opposed the idea of army handling public and political concerns. Normally, if army is involved in counter-terrorists related activities, they are usually not allowed to arrest or detain people but in Pakistan army were granted such permissions.

4. Policies being influenced by Political activities

The most apparent reason of every policy that is prepared for the goodwill of country failing badly is the political interference in the honest and transparent departments. Succeeding governments in Pakistan have used police as a mere tool to suppress the opposition political parties in the name of policy benefit, while the army men ruling the country have utilized police in suppressing the difference of opinion from anyone. In a country, where police force rather maintaining law and order becomes a threat and risk for the security of the locals, corruption is due to flourish. Everyone wants to fulfill his pockets and walk away and for this very purpose they are ready to not just condemn corruption but to support it. The higher level officials are appointed on the merit of their readiness to accept illegal orders, abuse the law and molest other political threats. In return, they are allowed to fulfill their illegal needs by using any means possible including corruption and loot the country with their fellows and masters.

The appointment of police in specific regions was made possible only on the recommendation of the political personalities. This made the junior staff unable to perform honestly and they also became indulged in illegal activities like their masters. Until a corrupt officer is the head of a specific sector, its internal accountability is not possible and as a trickle-down effect, corruption flourishes in the rank and file of the police establishment.

5. Professional Stifling in the Lower Ranks

The British system for the police force is still followed and implemented in the State of Pakistan (Michael, 2007). Royal Irish Constabulary was the pattern on which it was created; its main reason was to handle and get the better of the population and not to provide any kind of public service (Abbas, 2011). Until the end, the

illiterate and somewhat literate were appointed into the lower ranks. People selected were recruited into the lower Ranks with a percentage of 90%, with head constable or constable designation (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Department, 2018). There was no urge found for promotion in the hearts of lower ranks personells. They also lacked proper expernce mandatory for policing (Abbas, 2013). They kept providing their service until the age of sixty years after which they were retired. They were not like army troops or anything like that. For almost ten years they kept working at the same level without any urge for improvement.

Today, even there exist some high-up posts in the modern police system; most of the people are working as a constable. The members of other forces choke professionally, with no room for promotion or being selected in the conventional police system. This kind of system only provides frustration for all the police employees as their salaries are very low this they then move towards bribery and other illegal means to fulfil their needs. An HR expert commented that employees are highly motivated by the thought of being promoted to a higher level. There is not enthusiasm for police officers who work in such a gloomy and grim environment where there is not concept of promotion. The only outcome of such dull system would be the police officers abusing their powers and indulging themselves into illegal activities.

6. Abuse of the Lower Ranks

A credible system which will work efficiently and adequately will insure proper rewarding and punishments for those deserving is not present currently and it only delays any kind of reform. Theoretically, the performance of a police officer during the training course and the feedback he receives every year from his supervisor should be the merit calculator for his career advancement. Both the witnessing of the strict treatment handed out to lower rank individuals by their supervisors, and oppositely the absence of any kind of disciplinary action taken against the high ranked police officers is equally depressing. According to a calculation, there exists an imbalance in the amount of criticism received by the police department as the lower ranks officers are criticized more often. There exists no or very rare punishments for any officer of deputy superintendent level or above. Almost 54,800 officials were given punishments in the Punjab police during a single year. While 34,061 punishments were received by lower rank officers and on the other hand 18,820 officers at the assistant sub-inspector and sub-inspector rank were punished. Opposing this, officers of deputy superintendent level or above were punished only 32 times (Police report, 2011). Not a single senior police officer at the rank of superintendent of police or above was punished.

7. Political Blackmailing in the Hiring Process

Lastly, prizes, postings, promotions and training locations are selected on the demand of dominating individuals exacerbating a structure which is already full of flaws. Undeserving promotions and appointments to higher scales are the building block of such nepotism which leads to disempowerment of honest and reliable officers. Moreover, criticism is faced by those officers who do not want to abide by the illegal orders from corrupt political personnel's. Hence the officers who do not want to lose their jobs much get along with the nepotism. As a consequence, the interests of the officers are misplaced as they want to work for the betterment of their heads and not for the country. The appointment of officials on the suggestions of the political leaders only leaves the police officers prone to exploitation which makes them corrupt. It would be childish to think that police officers who receive such a low income would show any sympathy towards the public.

8. Gothic Thinking

The police department suffering through nepotism adopts old-fashioned and feudal mindset when they started receiving dictation from there leadership. A own circle of benefits is created by the police officer who is appointed on a major rank with the help of nepotism. He keeps benefiting and filling his pockets from the system while following the orders of his master and not paying any attention to the rules and regulations.

9. Constitutional Issues

In regards to the police department, a hurdle exists in creating police reforms because of defective arrangements in the pre-existing constitution. During the last sixty years, multiple instances in which martial law were initiated left the police investment to be minimal; the police sector was not much importance in the eyes of the army. However financial limitation are usually blamed as a hurdle in the reforms, the real issues lies within the government where the leaders have lost their will and do not form any kind of plans to improve the police sector (Jami, 1997). A big budget is not required for a reasonable reform in the police department but the political leaders do not wish to support any kind of betterment of police force. Hence, to create a police force which can be on par with those in the Western countries, the political leaders must have their priorities places correctly and federal and provincial leaders should be on the same page. Ever since the incident of September 11, 2001 in USA, Pakistan's Law and order situation has evolved drastically. The police should not surrender to older tradition anymore if they want to improve.

10. Crime-Terror nexus

During the past few decades, the terrorist organizations in the province have adopted new strategies to carry their activities in collaboration with criminal groups (Hussain, 2012). While the time after the cold-war, drop in sponsorship has forced most of the terrorist groups to find financial and material support elsewhere. After the 9/11 incident, the area for terrorist where they could hide kept getting tighter and tighter. The global "War on

Terrorism,” and specially the restriction on financial aiding system for the terrorist, caused the inter-country terrorists to convert themselves into traditional criminals and join criminal gangs (Hussain, 2012). On the other side, criminal syndicates started looking for security umbrella from terrorist organizations so the significant convergence of interests in both groups brought them together and they started targeting police personnel, check posts and vehicles (Jamal, 2015).

11. Lack of cooperation

Another drawback, affecting the efficiency of police in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is lack of coordination and cooperation among police personnel and the local community. The police department usually takes as corrupt institute and criticized for their personal interests. Therefore, locals try to avoid police personnel or officers.

12. Lack of sophisticated weapons

Darra and Bannu are full of shops that can copy the sophisticated weapons. These weapons were used in illegal and criminal activities and rarely have a record of sale and documentation (Khan, 2013). However, the weapons used in the police department are not advanced to meet the security demands of the contemporary stage.

13. Awareness of counter-terrorism

Institutions like military, intelligence sectors and civil military forces are responsible for providing police force with reasonable intelligence on various crimes while they are mainly responsible for maintain law and order situation in the society. Nevertheless, in Pakistan the police forces are strained to abandon their primary role in the inner security of the country and surrender to intelligence institutions, military Rangers and border Crops. Retired army officers are appointed as the head of the countries intelligence agencies and departments. As a result, the army chief is expected and looked upon by the political leaders to solve major issues concerning terrorism (the army chief) to take charge of all the operations launched against terrorist and criminals. Currently, whole Pakistan and the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa especially, suffer from the absence of an adequate counter-terrorism work plan, and the more alarming point is that they don't even bother to create a strategy. A fourteen point resolution on 22 October 2008 was put forward by the Parliament Security (Ghauri and Bilal, 2008).

A document comprising of twenty three pages were formed by a committee of 17-men for Parliament related to the policy of national security in the support of the previous resolution. The wishes of Pakistan people were included in the resolution and its succeeding policy. Unluckily, no attention had been paid to these policies by the government and the concerning department had also discarded the policy. In 2009, prime minister created National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) with a main mission of supporting policies of counter-terrorism (Zaheed, 2015). The Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) previous Director General Tariq Pervez headed the agency; He was a qualified man to handle terrorism related issues. But soon after the institute was formed, its functioning started facing different obstacles in its way of creating an effect counter-terrorism policy. Traditionally these kinds of institutions were handles by the Prime Minister but it came as a surprise when this bureau was headed by Minister of Interior. The bureau was soon left in a non-functioning situation. Hence, no proper counter-terrorism policy is currently as Pakistan's disposal. The story of National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) unveils the incompetent leaders running Pakistan.

Thus keeping in view the role of police in counter-terrorism as one of the primary duties allocated to the officer of the station house and his subordinates. New SOPs of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa police record major concerns and sensitizing police officer to be responsive to the behavior of terrorism, which they have to come across during their regular jobs. Organized crime, the involvement of the criminals for money, extortion, and trafficking of narcotics is openly related to funding of Pakistan's Tehrik-i-Taliban and other groups of the terrorist (Rana, 2014). Hence the role of police has always been aimed to establish law and security in the province, and the strategies and policies have changed with time to meet the security demands to meet contemporary challenges but roads are still long to reform police department in new models. These reforms cannot be achieved without the cooperation of the local community, political agents and security agencies.

14. Miscellaneous reforms

To investigate the crime evidence and facilitate the criminal investigation, a forensic science laboratory is about to be complete in Swat. The lab is equipped with sophisticated machinery and laboratory instruments. The mobile units are designed and trained to investigate the cases of terrorism and homicide crimes. Improved police salaries, provision of constabulary, direct admission to the Police Command during Internal Command Access Line and speedy track support of officials during the commission on public service were designed to keep the loyalty of officers towards department.

Inside Police stations; Dispute Resolution Councils (DRC); Police Assistant Line (PAL); Online FIR Registration and creation of Help desks operated by female are other steps to improve performance of police department in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Although these Police reforms are improving slowly, there is an improvement in the way people perceived the Police of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa which is set as a modernizer for police dependability and answerability of the department of public service. Despite having made considerable achievements for organized crimes, the Police

of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has an enormous challenge ahead in dealing with Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) reaction.

A highest ranking police officer, Inspector General Police (IGP) is not given free hand to perform independently. Politicians station their own blue-eyed police officers to discharge duties. According to a report, Inspector General of Police (IGP) of each province has not been on his seat for more than eight months on average. But now for some time, highest police officials are discharging their duties, especially in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Similarly, lower police officials do not get enough time to implement policies. Stability of tenure is considered a yardstick for the success of an officer. London Metropolitan Police Commissioner is appointed for five years under police Act 1996 of United Kingdom. So that uninterrupted tenure to be given to officer; this reduces chances of political manipulation because the officer will feel secure by having a fixed tenure. In Pakistan, long-term policies regarding countering terrorism can work only when police chief will have the freedom to exercise his powers

Conclusion And Analysis

Instead of numerous strategies by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa administration, the Police department is still facing challenges in peace keeping missions due to enormous administrative, financial and infrastructural problems. Further, in historical domain, police has been drawing powers from the law of 1861 that was the product of British era, which was orchestrated to deal with the socio-political situation of that time. Here in the 21st century, Pakistan needs new laws according to the prevailing situation. Politicians must pay full attention in bringing new laws of policing. All the provinces have different laws regarding police. Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are enjoying amended versions of 2002 police order whereas Sindh and Baluchistan are still living under colonial-era laws. The absence of modern laws of policing has reduced the proportion of transparency and accountability for police. Punjab Police launched the Online FIR first time in policing history now Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is doing the same thing with the help of Punjab government. A move by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Sindh police to have the option of online First Information Report (FIR) is a welcome step. The nation will have to introduce modern legislation and cutting-edge technology for counter-terrorism.

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